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Understanding Students' Behaviors in Using University Facilities

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Abstract

This study explores the natural and salient behaviors of university students within key areas of the campus, focusing on both social and personal aspects of their actions. Specifically, the research aims to identify patterns of student behavior in three primary locations: the library, learning halls, and classrooms. Using a qualitative observational approach, the researchers observed students over a five-day period, accumulating 50 hours of data. Behaviors were categorized based on how students interacted with the facilities: using them for studying (FLS), using technology (FT), resting or lounging (FRL), mismanaging the space (FNMP), and properly managing the space (FMP). Findings revealed that studying, technology use, and resting were most common in libraries and learning halls, while classroom behavior mostly involved proper management of space. Mismanagement of facilities was seen only in learning halls. Importantly, the study uncovered a complex, non-linear interaction of behaviors, often overlapping within the same space. This research offers valuable insights into how students of the University of St. Louis Tuguegarao, particularly those in the Bishop Constant Jurgens Campus, use and manage campus facilities.

Keywords: *school facilities, attitudes towards common spaces, school facility management, campus facilities, learning environments*

Introduction

Schools are often considered a student's second home, providing not only academic instruction but also fostering personal growth. As educational institutions evolve to meet the diverse needs of learners, the design and functionality of school facilities have undergone significant changes. Modern schools now offer a wide range of specialized facilities aimed at enhancing the learning experience. While there is a substantial body of research on how the school environment influences academic performance, there has been less attention on how students interact with and perceive these facilities, and how their behavior reflects their attitudes toward the school environment.

Learning facilities can be broadly defined as spaces designed to support various activities aimed at achieving educational objectives (Frameiliada et.al., 2023; Nugroho & Wibowo, 2020). These facilities play a crucial role in shaping the quality of education students receive. Ranti et.al. (2022) highlights that the effectiveness of the learning process is closely tied to the optimal availability, utilization, and management of educational facilities and infrastructure. A conducive environment created by well-maintained and properly used facilities can lead to improved learning experiences and help students manage their academic responsibilities more effectively.

Previous studies, such as Sianipar et.al. (2023), suggest that the completeness and quality of school facilities encourage student learning and motivation. However, the mere availability of these resources does not guarantee academic success. The way in which students engage with and utilize these facilities is equally critical. The behavioral dynamics in these spaces – whether students are using facilities appropriately or not – can have significant implications for the overall learning environment (Frameiliada et.al., 2023).

Despite this, few studies have examined the link between the student behavior and facility management, leaving a gap in the understanding of how attitudes toward school facilities might affect academic and personal outcomes.

University of Saint Louis expanded to a new campus to cater to students taking course in Accountancy, Business, Education, Criminology, Arts and Psychology. In its efforts to provide quality education to students, it continues to invest in modern and innovative learning spaces. With this effort of the university, the researchers saw the necessity to investigate how students perceive and interact with these facilities.

The behavior of students in using the university facilities provides insight into an effective facility management. The patterns of observed behavior can inform future improvements in facility planning and management. A survey was conducted about the satisfaction of the students of the school facilities, and revealed a high level of satisfaction. This observational study serves as a basis in drafting practical guidelines in the use of the facilities, so that it could maintain the high satisfaction of the students to school facilities, and consequently get most of the benefit of a satisfactory learning space.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the attitudes of students toward school facilities, specifically examining how these attitudes influence the use, management, and effectiveness of these facilities in enhancing their overall learning experience and personal development. Specifically, it answers the following questions

1. What behaviors are commonly exhibited by students when using school facilities?
2. What factors influence their proper or improper use?

Literature Review

Attitudes of Students Towards the Use of School Facilities

The quality and state of school facilities have long been recognized as crucial factors in shaping student learning experiences and academic outcomes (Schneider, 2002). Studies have consistently demonstrated that the physical environment of a school, including factors such as lighting, temperature, air quality, and spatial configuration, can significantly impact student performance and well-being (Schneider, 2002; and Uline & Tschannen-Moran, 2008).

One important aspect of this relationship is the attitude of students towards the use of school facilities. Recent research has shown that students' perceptions and experiences with their school's physical infrastructure can have a significant influence on their academic motivation, engagement, and overall satisfaction with their educational environment.

Several studies have explored the connection between school facilities and student attitudes. For instance, a review by McGuffey found that the quality of school buildings, including features like science laboratories and libraries, was linked to higher student achievement (Uline & Tschannen-Moran, 2008). Similarly, Simpeh's work highlighted the importance of parameters such as lighting, ventilation, and temperature in affecting the health and safety of students and staff within the academic environment (Abisuga et al., 2016).

Furthermore, research has emphasized that the design and condition of school facilities can impact the school's climate and culture, which in turn can shape students' perceptions and attitudes. As the review by McGuffey suggests, the physical environment of a school can serve as a reflection of the institution's values and priorities, influencing students' sense of belonging and investment in their educational experience.

Ultimately, the existing body of literature underscores the crucial role that school facilities play in shaping students' attitudes and learning experiences. By ensuring that educational institutions provide clean, comfortable, and well-maintained physical spaces, schools can foster a positive learning environment that supports student engagement, achievement, and overall well-being (Abisuga et al., 2016; Schneider, 2002; Uline & Tschannen-Moran, 2008; and Hopland, 2013).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative design that integrated both participatory and non-participatory observation to capture the complexities of human behavior in a natural setting. By combining these two observational approaches, the researchers were able to offer a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation. Non-participatory observation allows the researchers to observe participants without influencing their actions, providing an objective lens through which natural behaviors can emerge. This method collects data on observable actions and interactions, which is crucial for identifying broader patterns and dynamics within the studied environment.

Conversely, participatory observation involves the researchers actively engaging with the environment, allowing them to experience the context firsthand. This deeper immersion facilitates access to rich insights into the lived experiences, emotions, and motivations of the participants—elements that cannot be fully understood through external observation alone. Through active participation, the researchers gain a more intimate understanding of the underlying factors shaping behaviors and interactions.

By combining both participatory and non-participatory observation, the researchers are able to construct a more nuanced and well-rounded picture of the phenomena. This approach integrates both objective, observable data and subjective, context-driven insights, providing a fuller, more holistic understanding of human behavior in its natural setting.

Participants

The participants of the study were the college students from the School of Education, Criminology, Arts and Psychology (SECAP) and the School of Accountancy, Business and Hospitality (SABH), who were having who were using the school facilities at the new campus of the University of Saint Louis, which is the Bishop Constant Jurgens Campus (BCJC).

Instrument

The researchers used an unobtrusive method, observing behavior in a natural setting while avoiding prominent engagements that might evoke reactions from the participants. They also utilized a bulleted note-taking scheme that features time-stamped data (i.e., morning and afternoon) gathered from the three identified areas of observation captured in real-time.

Procedure

Data were gathered from multiple students of different year levels. Subjects were observed for 50 hours in total across six days. Observations were routinely conducted in the morning and afternoon at three locations: the campus learning halls (LH), classrooms, and library. Observation for the classroom was conducted through a participatory observation method; the researchers were part of the group. The researchers employed a unified note-taking scheme using Google documents, and each observation was distinguished by

labeling the time stamp. Researchers were careful not to interfere with the natural occurrence of behavior as it may affect the observation results.

The study used an assignment strategy for note-taking; two observers were assigned for each location and were tasked to observe during the entire duration allotted for data gathering. It is worth noting that the researchers are to inspect the observation area to fully grasp the locale and enhance the scope of the data gathering. It may be essential to raise an interesting aspect of the observation—the shift from face-to-face classes to online set-up. While it only occurred briefly, data gathering during the online setup emphasized significant detail.

Data Analysis

The narrative analysis of observational data highlighted the nascent themes underlying students' behaviors. Using narrative analysis allows the researchers to describe and extract nuanced meanings from the observation. This analysis was also used to capture the explicit and implicit precedents of behavior as they occurred in real-time.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers did not engage in any ethical misconduct. All information obtained in this study was used for academic purposes only. By adopting a non-intrusive method of acquiring data, the researchers ensured that their presence would be as discreet as possible and that no physical or psychological distress was inflicted among the participants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the key findings of the study, specifically the comprehensive summary of the data collected and analyzed. This highlights the patterns of behaviors uncovered. The findings are presented systematically following the research questions and objectives. This presents the raw results that form the foundation for the subsequent analysis and conclusions.

Table 1. *The narrative analysis results indicate five key emerging details that underline multiple categories of student behavior over three identified locations*

Categories	High Prevalence (In Terms Of Location)	Low Prevalence (In Terms Of Location)
Facilities being used for learning/studying (FLS)	Learning Hall and Library	Classrooms
Facilities being used with technology (FT)	Learning Hall and Library	Classrooms
Facilities being used for resting/lounging (FRL)	Learning Hall and Library	Classrooms
Facilities being used but not managed properly (FNMP)	Learning Hall	Library and Classroom
Facilities being used and managed properly (FMP)	Library and Classroom	Learning halls

The table categorizes the usage of various facilities across different contexts, specifically comparing those with high and low prevalence based on location. The facilities are grouped into five categories: Facilities being used for learning/studying (FLS), Facilities being used with technology (FT), Facilities being used for resting/lounging (FRL), Facilities being used but not managed properly (FNMP), and Facilities being used and managed properly (FMP).

In terms of location prevalence, Learning Halls and Libraries are more commonly used for learning, technology integration, and resting, while Classrooms show lower usage in these contexts. However, when considering management practices, Learning Halls have a high prevalence of being used but not managed properly, whereas Libraries and Classrooms are better managed and show a higher prevalence of proper usage. Conversely, Learning Halls are less frequently managed properly, indicating discrepancies in how these spaces are utilized and maintained.

Figure 1. *The pattern of behavior in learning halls across all observation*

Based on the chart FMP occurred the most in day 3, along with FT and FNMP. FRL was observed on both day 3 and day 6. FLS was observed to be consistent for two days, from day 4 to day 5.

A particular concern is the occurrence of FMP in learning halls, along with other themes. The researchers ruled out the effect of the

date as it was a typical class schedule for students. However, based on the narrative analysis of the data, observational data revealed that the resources for the area, such as chairs and tables, were insufficient; this was not incidental, as it was also detected on other days of observation. The scenario may have prompted students to use what was available—the quality and quantity of school resources in influencing students' behavior, such as how they would react to an incomplete set of chairs or tables (would tendencies to engage in misusage increase?) is a perspective worth investigating.

Figure 2. *The pattern of behavior in the library across all observation*

Based on the data, FMP and FRL were observed most frequently on day 3. FT was observed the most on day 2. FLS and FNMP were observed the most on day 4.

Coincidentally, FMP was also prevalent in libraries for Day 3. Based on the narrative for this particular area, researchers were able to find instances of “student assistants” manning some key portions of the library such as the ID scanning station, bookshelves, and baggage counters. These observations were included in the analysis as contributory antecedents to FMP.

Figure 3. *The pattern of behavior in the classrooms across all observation*

Based on the data, FLS was observed on both day 2 and day 5 only. FRL was only observed on day 2 and day 3. Interestingly, FT was only observed on day 5. FNMP was observed the most on days 2 and 4, while FMP was observed the most on days 2, 4, and 6.

The study utilized a qualitative, observational design (participatory and non-participatory) among multiple students. Based on the analysis of various observations, the diversity and complexity of behavior was a crucial outcome of the process. Particular details were drawn out of the narratives: Facilities being used for learning/studying, Facilities being used with technology, Facilities being used for resting/lounging, Facilities being used but not appropriately managed, and Facilities being used and managed correctly.

Facilities being used for learning/studying. The researchers identified certain participants using learning halls and library facilities for learning purposes. The proliferation of findings indicates that these behaviors may be contingent on context and environment—that is, libraries are made for learning, and the same goes for learning halls. A way to analyze the observation is to look at the environmental and psychological antecedents. According to behavior as a consequence of attitudes, Icek Ajzen and Martin Fishbein (1977, 2005) emphasized in their Theory of Planned Behavior that stronger attitudes or beliefs about something make behavior more likely to occur. A jogger who believes jogging would benefit his health greatly will continue to jog. By implication, students who hold strong beliefs about the need to study may be prompted to do so. Structurally speaking, adequately spaced facilities with minimal distractions provide a more conducive learning environment (Ikegbusi, Manafa, & Iheanacho, 2022).

The students' behavior geared over learning/studying in these locations persisted throughout the observation period—such observation yielded a consistent result, demonstrating the uniformity and frequency of behavior. This result may present initial supporting evidence on the effectiveness of these locations in catering to the needs of the participants—especially concerning its quality and adequacy. As contended by Jagero (2013), school facilities must provide sufficiency and effectiveness as they contribute to the quality of output—this implies that facilities and other facets of the school may influence the students' performance. On a similar note, Lopez et al. (2019)

found that facilities, especially the completeness of equipment, proved to be effective in facilitating academic improvement among students. However, when it comes to practical planning, academic-related facilities arguably offer optimal opportunities for learning. As emphasized by McGowen (2007), developers should prioritize academic facilities such as classrooms and libraries over supporting facilities such as learning halls.

According to a theory developed by Kurt Lewin in 1936, known as The Person-Environment Fit Theory, an individual's behavior is dependent on their characteristics and environment. With that, an ideal behavior will only be realized if the individual would perceive the environment as something that is of great fit or match to that of their characteristics, or perhaps preferences. Based on a diagram presented by Stoll & Trautwein (2017) on the Dynamic Processes Between Person and Fit Environment, this "environment" is believed to influence how a person would perform (e.g. low congruence is associated with active adjustment, quitting, and more. Applying this perspective and looking at how students intend to maximize these facilities as part of their learning journey, it may be implied that the three identified areas of observation have met their main objective — to promote academic engagement and allow students to attend to their perceived learning responsibilities.

Facilities being used with technology. For years, the nature of the educational setting has changed significantly due to the rise of digital technology. ICT integrations have become a part of learning strategies, and policies have been implemented worldwide to adapt to this change (Diola & Omana, 2024). The expansive and dynamic use of technologies like electronics inside school facilities is not necessarily detrimental. As emphasized in the study of Vicky et al. (2023), gadgets are extremely useful in improving student performance. And just as gadgets provide access to educational apps, students' academic performance also increased, as observed in a study conducted by Ababa et al., (2021). At the same time, up-to-date technology and interactive tools support innovative teaching methods that cater to varying learning styles (Tacadao & Lumapenet, 2024). Based on the study's results, it was found that of all the behaviors identified and assessed, students commonly use their gadgets in these locations either to learn, relax, or use them without a clear purpose. This behavior then overlapped with other behaviors, such as learning and resting. In an observational study by Catalano et al. (2014), mobile phones can be distracting, but students still use them for study-related activities. However, in the same study, technologies are highly encouraged to be integrated into school facilities, particularly libraries, to optimize the academic experience. The behavior was also observed with other actions, such as participants being unable to fix utilities after using their phones or being preoccupied with them, resulting in perceived negligence.

Facilities being used for resting/lounging While these spaces were primarily designed to foster academic engagement and provide students with the means to fulfill their academic responsibilities, it was not explicitly mandated that they be used in a strictly formal manner. Recent developments within the school facilities, particularly in the library, have introduced lounging areas in each of the university's libraries. Naturally, this category was observed most frequently in locations where it is clearly being promoted. In the library, it was expected that this behavior would be observed throughout as it allows an opportunity to rest and relax amidst academic activities. This emerging theme poses a clear understanding of how school facilities could cater openly to students who wish to rest.

As postulated in a study concerning adolescents by Roessler and Grove (2018), there are many factors affecting students' resting time, rest deprivation may be disruptive in their day-to-day activities in school. One possible solution to this is to recalibrate and integrate facilities in schools that offer particular needs such as sleep for students. However, such cannot be said with learning halls, especially since they are the most exposed location to open air. Regardless, participants are still observed to frequent the place to rest. Unlike in libraries, where it is usually managed by a librarian or school authorities, learning halls are not typically managed by direct authority; instead, they are managed by school maintenance. While schools strive to establish well-designed facilities, they should also promote maintenance practices. Concerned authorities should cultivate sustainable approaches that maximize their capabilities (Otchere et al., 2019).

Facilities being used but not managed properly. The observation results show a high incidence of unattended school utilities, mainly in the school's learning halls and classrooms. There are sublayers to this behavior that the researchers were able to extract; firstly, it was evident in the observation that some participants take passive and active roles in the overall organization of these utilities—this study describes disorderly behavior in the context of school facilities as whether it is being appropriately used/ placed in its designated area or not. The results of the narrative analysis show a strong prevalence of participants actively engaging in disorderly behavior—the students partook in disarranging the chairs or leaving fans open after usage; intentionality is ambiguous because data is insufficient to include the assumption that the participants intended them to happen. Passive disorderly behavior is defined as generally seeing things happening but not doing anything; some participants were observed to be engaging in passive behaviors where they first saw things scattered everywhere and fans not closed—they were not directly involved in the situation but failed to act on them. The physical environment itself may impact the way students behave. El-Nemr (2022) have found that school buildings are related to student disciplinary incidents, the study argues that cosmetic aspects of a building can have an impact on the frequency of violative behavior which varies across groups. The lack of a supervising authority may influence how behaviors can turn out and may mediate these problems as some form of discipline or regulation (Way, 2011; Ikegbusi et al., 2022). Disorderly behavior might also have been influenced by the things they observe among their peers. Their behavior and decisions may have been influenced by what they have observed from others (Gariépy et al., 2014). However, another point of interest is that the same study outlined that understanding student perception of discipline and authority is fundamental to understanding how discipline influences student behavior; thus, a more thorough investigation of the matter must be conducted into the personal accounts of the participants.

Facilities being used and managed properly. Based on the analysis, this behavior is usually observed in libraries and classrooms. Facilities being used and managed properly show contrasting differences with disorderly behavior based on situational forces. Participants are observed to deviate from disorderly behavior when confronted with the obligation to do so—being instructed to manage the facility properly. This may support the evidence that teachers play a crucial role in developing a more conducive and participative environment for students (Reeve & Shin, 2019; Otchere et al., 2019). It can also be noted from the observation that although there is a presence of authority figures in these areas, students themselves take an active part in organizing the facilities without the need for explicit instructions. Participants were also observed to be managing the facilities that were used previously. Additionally, a distinct pattern of behavior of participants using their materials to reserve seats was recorded most frequently in the library; although it is not part of any category, it might be an interesting study to investigate.

Conclusions

This study reveals an array of behaviors that students exhibit in relation to university facilities, highlighting both the effective and ineffective use of these spaces. Students utilized learning halls, libraries, and technology-equipped areas as intended for academic engagement and study. The presence of flexible spaces, digital resources, and restful areas promoted not only academic productivity but also emotional well-being. However, observed behaviors also revealed instances of poor management and neglect of resources, particularly in areas with limited oversight or inconsistent maintenance. The results suggest that the physical environment influences student behavior, with proper management and alignment to student's needs leading to positive and productive use, while lack of authority or organization may contribute to disorderly conduct.

Based from the conclusion above, the following are recommended:

Assign dedicated person to oversee areas such as learning halls and other o shared spaces.

A guideline on the use of shared spaces should be posted on a conspicuous area to promote sustainable facility usage, until a culture of shared responsibility is being established.

Include facility etiquette as a topic in social science subjects to promote culture of respect and responsibility

Facility manager could consider allocating a space for rest, as multi-functional spaces are frequently used for rest.

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